

Here are links to some resources that could help you grow in your journey as bioinformaticians in Open Science, as shared by our expert facilitators:

Dr. Amonida Zadissa shared this:

- COVID-19 portals
 - [GISAID](#)
 - [COVID-19 Data Portal](#)
- FAIR & CARE principles
 - [FAIR](#)
 - [CARE](#)
- [Scientific Data](#) - publish your datasets
- Data management plan (DMP) resources
 - [DMPTool](#) has public DMPs
 - [Example set of DMPs](#)
 - NWU has good coverage of Research Datamanagement Plan and also training
 - [Research Data Management: Data Management Plan](#)
 - Check out their [best practices](#)
- Tutorials and courses
 - [Galaxy](#)
 - Comprehensive platform for data fetching, data analysis, etc
 - [EMBL-EBI On demand training](#)
 - Lots of materials across many different topics, all freely available
 - I'd recommend the following ones if you're just about to start with bioinformatics:
 - [Introductory bioinformatics](#)
 - [Biostatistics](#)
 - [Finding and using publicly available data](#)
- R for bioinformaticians - these are resources that I recommend to our students in UK DRI
 - [Code academy](#)
 - [Cancer Research UK Bitesize R](#)
 - [UC Davis Introduction to R for bioinformatics](#)
 - [EMBL-EBI R for immunology bioinformatics](#)
 - [Data carpentry](#)

The exercises and the tutorials, resources are also on [my GitHub account](#).

Dr. Toby Hodges shared this:

1. <https://github.com/>
2. <https://sandbox.zenodo.org/>

3. [The Turing Way's chapter on licensing](#) for open source projects
4. [Markdown cheatsheet](#)
5. [Software Carpentry: Version Control with Git](#)
6. Learn more about GitHub Pages:
 - a. [GitHub docs](#)
 - b. [Sarah Gibson's lesson about building a website with Hugo and GitHub Pages](#)
7. Toby works for [The Carpentries](#)
8. Two recommended resources to keep learning:
9. + Software Carpentry: Version Control with Git
<https://swcarpentry.github.io/git-novice/>
10. + Turing Way: Getting Started with GitHub
<https://book.the-turing-way.org/collaboration/github-novice>
11. [Community Events | The Carpentries](#)